

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF MICROELEMENTS IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA IN CHILDREN

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Abstract.

Purpose of the study to study possible pathogenetic mechanisms of bronchial asthma associated with microelement disorders in children.

Materials and methods. The study group included 83 children with bronchial asthma of varying degrees, who underwent inpatient treatment at the allergological department of the Tashkent Medical Academy. The average age of children was 8.05 ± 0.12 . The control group consisted of 32 relatively healthy children of the same age who did not have a history of atopic, chronic bronchopulmonary diseases and who had the last acute respiratory disease for more than 1 month before the study. Exclusion Criteria: Children who took micronutrients or vitamin supplements. Based on the data obtained, it was found that the vast majority of the examined patients had mild BA (65.6%), moderate in 20.6% of the examined and severe in 13.7% of cases. An analysis of the blood serum indicators made it possible to establish that there are significant differences between the indicators reflecting the content of macroelements in children with asthma from those in the control group (Table 1). Moreover, it is important to note that the content of these macroelements in patients with varying degrees of severity of the disease, on the contrary, did not have significant differences. It has been established that patients with BA have a significant increase in phosphorus content, as well as a decrease in the level of calcium, magnesium and zinc in blood serum compared with patients in the control group. The obtained data on changes in macroelemental homeostasis indicate an important role of diselementoses in the pathogenesis of AD. A change in the concentration of these substances is a significant factor contributing to the progression of chronic inflammation in the bronchi and requiring correction of the therapy in children.

Key words.

Macro- and microelements, bronchial asthma, children.

Introduction

The steady increase in the prevalence of bronchial asthma in the structure of childhood morbidity, as well as its conditionality due to environmental problems, is a serious problem for public health in most countries of the world. In recent years, there has been a tendency towards an early onset and more severe course of the disease, which reduces the quality of life of sick children and contributes to an increase in childhood disability.

According to the modern concept, the pathogenetic basis of bronchial asthma is chronic allergic inflammation of the bronchi. The exact causes of its occurrence have not yet been established [1, 2, 3], and therefore the need for further research into the pathogenesis of the disease is obvious. First of all, many molecular, cellular and immune mechanisms that contribute to the emergence and maintenance of chronic inflammation and determine its intensity require study [2, 4, 5].

Numerous, but scattered and contradictory facts have been accumulated over the past forty years, indicating the participation of minerals and trace elements in various parts of the pathogenesis of allergies [6, 7]. At the same time, the number of clinical studies on the metabolism of macro- and microelements in bronchial asthma is limited.

However, as allergy appears to be an important predictor of asthma, it is likely the factors that protect against allergy may be important in asthma prevention [8, 9]. One of a number of environmental factors that has been proposed as a reason for the escalation in asthma prevalence is a decreasing intake of dietary antioxidants, and some observational studies have shown significant associations between asthma and antioxidants, such as vitamins C and E [6].

Recently, it has been hypothesized that essential elements may play important roles in asthma genesis since they take part in oxidative stress reactions as cofactors of antioxidant enzymes. Antioxidant and trace element deficiencies seem to be important factors in this regard [8].

Recent studies, according to models of experimental antigen challenge and clinical and preclinical findings, showed that asthma attacks correlate with immediate release of high levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS), including superoxide and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), which as free radicals can affect asthma status and may intervene with the late asthmatic response. Recent experimental models and clinical studies of asthma indicate some mechanistic link between intermittent excessive oxidative processes and various inflammatory diseases, especially asthma [5].

Pathophysiology of asthma, bronchial airway, and lung inflammation can result from a lack of, or failure to, activate antioxidants, or from a lack of their reactivity with enzymes. Serum superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity is dramatically lower in people with asthmatic lungs than in normal people. It has been hypothesized that CuZnSOD activity and asthma are related (9). Although the cause of the greater than 50% reduction of SOD activity in asthma is unclear, it is thought that alterations in MnSOD and CuZnSOD are involved [5, 8].

Because asthma has been demonstrated to involve increased oxidative stress, trace elements, including copper (Cu), selenium (Se), and zinc (Zn) have been hypothesized to play important roles in the pathogenesis of asthma. However, significant associations between their status and the prevalence or severity of asthma have not been consistently demonstrated in human studies. Despite numerous investigations of trace elements and their enzymes in asthma, the relationship is not well understood. This investigation highlights both the complex etiology of human asthma and the inherent problems with the investigated trace elements.

To date, the relationship between the development of certain multifactorial diseases and deficiency, excess or imbalance of macro- and microelements in the body has been proven [5, 6, 7, 8]. The effect of bioelements on the pathogenetic mechanisms of BA formation is insufficiently studied.

Purpose of the study – to study possible pathogenetic mechanisms of bronchial asthma associated with microelement disorders in children.

Materials and methods

The study group included 83 children with bronchial asthma of varying degrees, who underwent inpatient treatment at the allergological department of the Tashkent Medical Academy. The average age of children was 8.05 ± 0.12 . The control group consisted of 32 relatively healthy children of the same age who did not have a history of atopic, chronic bronchopulmonary diseases and who had the last acute respiratory disease for more than 1 month before the study. Exclusion Criteria: Children who took micronutrients or vitamin supplements.

The sensitivity of the receptor apparatus of the bronchial tree was studied by means of an inhalation-provocation test with histamine and metacholine by the dose method [3]. Standard histamine solutions were prepared from histamine phosphate powder and buffer phosphate salt solution in concentrations 0,125; 0,25; 0,5; 1; 2; 4; 8; 16 mg / ml. The methacholine solutions prepared from a powder of methacholine chloride and saline solution in the same concentrations. Measurements of forced exhalation volume (FEV1), forced expiratory vital capacity

(FVC), forced expiratory flow at 25,50.75% (FEF_{25, 50,75}) were performed 30 and 60 seconds after each inhalation. The test was stopped when FEV₁ decreased by 20 % or more and/or when clinical symptoms of bronchospasm appeared - when the threshold concentration (PK₂₀) was reached. Threshold sensitivity was assessed as high at PK₂₀ to 0.125–0.5 mg/ml, from 1 to 2 mg/ml - moderate, from 4 to 8 mg/ml - low, over 8 mg/ml - normal. The me content was determined by atomic absorption spectrometry (the substrate under study is blood serum) and x - ray fluorescence (the substrate under study is hair). All hair samples were subjected to the sample preparation according to the International Atomic Energy Agency requirements and guidelines "Screening methods to identify high-risk groups among workers in contact with toxic chemicals" approved by the Ministry of Health of the Uzbekistan (1998), No. 41 "Detection and correction of violations of the exchange of macro-and microelements", approved by the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan 15.09.2009. Energy-dispersive x-ray fluorescence elemental analysis was performed at the SR VEPP-3 elemental analysis station (Institute of nuclear physics in Uzbekistan). We determined the content of essential - Fe, I, Cu, Zn, Co, Cr, Mo, Se, Mn and toxic - As, Br, Ni, Rb, Sr, Zr, Nb, Au, Pb, Hg, Bi me, as well as the macronutrient Ca.

Upon admission, all children underwent a comprehensive clinical, laboratory and allergic-immunological examination. The study of mineral homeostasis in blood serum was carried out by X-ray fluorescence analysis (XRF). Statistical analysis was carried out using the program "OpenEpi 2009".

Results

Based on the data obtained, it was found that the vast majority of the examined patients had mild BA (65.6%), moderate in 20.6% of the examined and severe in 13.7% of cases.

An analysis of the blood serum indicators made it possible to establish that there are significant differences between the indicators reflecting the content of macroelements in children with asthma from those in the control group (Table 1). Moreover, it is important to note that the content of these macroelements in patients with varying degrees of severity of the disease, on the contrary, did not have significant differences.

In the future, the comparison of selenium and zinc concentrations in blood serum (as indicators of microelementosis at the organ level) was carried out in children with "hyperreactors", for a short time, under dynamic conditions) and hair tissue (as an assessment of long-term microelementosis, "chronic" deficiency).

The data obtained indicate an increase in the content of phosphorus in children with BA, compared with the control group. While the indicators of calcium, magnesium and iron, on the contrary, are lower in the group of patients ($p < 0.0001$).

This is important from the point of view of the pathogenesis of BA, since a decrease in the level of magnesium can lead to impaired contractility of the bronchi, because it is magnesium that activates adenylate cyclase, and it, in turn, catalyzes the formation of cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) and prevents degranulation of mast cells, thereby providing relaxation of the smooth muscles of the bronchi. The decrease in calcium levels may be due to the depletion of its pool during the intense contraction of bronchial smooth muscles during an exacerbation of the disease, and it also plays a role in maintaining chronic inflammation.

Table 1.

The content of microelements in children with BA, mmol/l

ED	Patients with asthma (n=83)	Comparison group (n=32)
Phosphorus, inorganic	2,1 ±0,17 mmol/l	0,92 ±0,086 mmol/l
Iron	8,6±1,04 mmol/l	9,1±1,22 mmol/l
Calcium	1,7±0,19 mmol/l	2,3±0,26 mmol/l
Magnesium	0,82±0,05 mmol/l	0,72±0,04 mmol/l
Vitamin D total (D2+D3)	24,36±1,96 ng/ml	29,45±2,11 ng/ml
Zinc	72,35±3,3 mg/dl	92,27±3,8 mg/dl

It is calcium that is able to cause the release of mast cell mediators, thereby contributing to an increase in the secretion of mucous glands and the movement of pro-inflammatory cells into the walls of the respiratory tract. Particular attention should be paid to the level of phosphorus in the blood serum: in patients with asthma, there is a significant increase in its content (2.1 [1.97; 3.2] mmol/l) compared with the control group (0.92 [0.49; 0.9] mmol/l) [$p < 0, 0001$].

Asthma is a chronic disease with airway inflammation characterized by reversible airflow obstruction. One outcome of asthma is bronchial hyper-responsiveness. Because trace elements play key roles in inflammation, they may affect asthma status [7].

In our study, no significant differences were found for serum Se concentrations between healthy controls and patients with allergic asthma. This

result agrees with previous reports that found no differences in serum Se concentrations between asthmatic patients and healthy individuals [9]. The data also showed no difference in serum Se concentrations between moderate and severe asthmatics. These results indicate that Se has no effect on allergic asthma severity.

Taking into account the fact that phosphorus is the main tissue-forming macroelement that is part of the phospholipids of cell membranes, including the respiratory epithelium, it can be assumed that an increase in the levels of this substance in the blood serum of patients with asthma may indicate a chronic inflammatory process in the bronchopulmonary system.

Also, in patients with clinical manifestations of bronchial asthma, a decrease in the level of vitamin D in the blood serum (24.36 ng/ml) was registered, compared with the control group (97.27 ng/ml) [$p < 0.0001$].

Discussion

Despite the special attention focused on the study of BA etiopathogenesis, the problem of mineral homeostasis disorders in patients with this pathology is poorly understood, and studies devoted to the study of this issue are often fragmentary without a comprehensive assessment of the identified disorders.

Zn concentrations were significantly lower in patients than in controls, although no correlation was found between Zn concentrations and disease severity. Since Zn concentrations were lower in patients with allergic asthma than in controls but no difference was seen between patients with moderate vs. severe asthma, we conclude that Zn deficiency may have a role in asthma onset but not progression [6]. Zn is an important trace element and its concentration is frequently used to evaluate inflammatory diseases [9]. Furthermore, many studies have reported that Zn deficiency can lead to a variety of complications, including growth retardation, delayed wound healing, chronic diarrhea, and increased susceptibility to infections [5]. It can also disturb the equilibrium between types 1 and 2 T helper cells, which causes increased inflammation; the same mechanism detected in allergic airway hypersensitivity [8]. A number of clinical studies have linked an increase in the incidence of asthma with low dietary Zn intake. Significant decreases in serum, plasma, and hair Zn levels have also been reported in some asthmatic individuals. Therefore, it is suggested that the deficiency of Zn may reduce antioxidant function and lead to increasing risk of bronchial asthma. Our data indicates that allergic asthma may be affected by low Zn levels and is consistent with data for non-allergic asthma and other inflammatory diseases.

Many previous studies have reported that the serum Cu concentrations in bronchial asthma patients tended to be higher than in healthy individuals. Cu/Zn-SOD is an antioxidant enzyme that contains Cu as an essential component. Our data showed that the Cu concentration in patients with allergic asthma was higher than that in the healthy control group, particularly in females. Some previous studies indicated that high Zn serum concentrations can lead to declines in both Cu/Zn-SOD and Cu concentrations, as Cu deficiency can reflect a high Zn concentration. So, the high serum Cu concentrations in patients in this investigation are further evidence of Cu Zn antagonism in the pathophysiology of asthma.

At the same time, the data obtained in the course of this study are consistent with the results obtained by other scientists. Thus, it has been proven that Ca ions are involved in the pathogenesis of BA. Moreover, researchers have already formulated the so-called "calcium" theory of the development of bronchial hyperreactivity syndrome. Few data suggest that Mg deficiency is associated with increased tracheobronchial hyperresponsiveness, pulmonary vascular resistance, and ventricular arrhythmias. In this regard, free radical processes are intensified, which lead to degeneration, necrosis of the epithelium of the respiratory tract and, as a result, to fibrotization and bronchoconstriction. All this indicates the need to continue research in this scientific direction and to search for biological markers of the severe course of BA.

Conclusion

It has been established that patients with BA have a significant increase in phosphorus content, as well as a decrease in the level of calcium, magnesium and zinc in blood serum compared with patients in the control group. The obtained data on changes in macroelemental homeostasis indicate an important role of diselementoses in the pathogenesis of BA. A change in the concentration of these substances is a significant factor contributing to the progression of chronic inflammation in the bronchi and requiring correction of the therapy in children.

In conclusion, we recommend that serum analysis of trace elements, especially Zn, be considered in the workup of intractable allergic asthma, and the administration of zinc supplements may be useful in the prevention and treatment of allergic asthma. Further studies conducted on intervention to change trace element level underlying structure function changes in asthma, and in particular in severe asthma, are needed to define the pathophysiology and biochemistry of asthma. If this paradigm holds, it will be important for the design of therapies.

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